

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

ETHNODEMOGRAPHIC SITUATION IN NAKHCHIVAN IN THE 19TH AND EARLY 20TH CENTURIES

Hasanov Sh.

PhD, Leading researcher of the

Institute of History and Ethnography named after A.A. Bakikhanov

ORCID: 0009-0008-0846-8739

Baku, Azerbaijan

ABSTRACT

During the 19th and early 20th centuries, the ethnic and demographic makeup of the cities in Northern Azerbaijan, as well as Nakhchivan, experienced significant changes. These changes were due to the resettlement policy of the Russian Empire, oppression of the local population, and the displacement of the local people from their land.

The Republic of Azerbaijan which regained its independence after the collapse of the Soviet Union still faces problems caused by the territorial policies of the Tsarist and Soviet empires. Therefore, it is extremely important to study the ethno-demographic landscape of any region and city of Azerbaijan in previous stages of history. This will help to determine the number of Azerbaijanis and other peoples who have historically lived in the region during different periods of history. Studying the number of peoples living in a particular region is especially important from the point of view of understanding mutual political, economic, and cultural ties, as well as the ethnic processes that have taken place.

The article examines the significant increase in the Armenian population in the territory of Nakhchivan over 100 years since the signing of the Turkmenchay Treaty.

Keywords: Ethno-demographic indicators, population of Azerbaijan, population of Nakhchivan, results of the Turkmenchay Treaty, resettlement policy of tsarism.

Introduction

Since the middle of the 20th century, the interest of researchers in demographic problems has significantly increased. New demographic trends have emerged, which are characterized by social and demographic factors, and the relationship between demographic facts and historical events. This innovation is a significant improvement compared to previous studies. It is also essential to have quantitative information about people from the perspective of studying ethnic history. The ethnic development of large nations differs significantly from the development of small ethnic communities, and cases of population decline can significantly affect their future history. It is important to study the number of people living in a specific region, particularly in terms of understanding cultural influence and ethnic processes happening between them.

The ethno-geographic situation of Northern Azerbaijan cities, including Nakhchivan, during the 19th and early 20th centuries, and the resettlement policy of the Russian Empire, which directly impacted this matter, is a significant issue that scholars regularly investigate. In the early 19th century, the government of Tsarist Russia implemented a policy of Christianization and Russification in Northern Azerbaijan. This colonial policy resulted in the introduction of various administrative divisions and the resettlement of other peoples, particularly Armenians, to Azerbaijan. The establishment of Armenian settlements in the Baku, Elizavetpol, Irevan, and partially Tbilisi governorates was accompanied by the oppression and displacement of the local population from their lands. The policy of Christianization and Russification on the historical territory of Azerbaijan continued during the Soviet era.

The Republic of Azerbaijan which regained its independence after the collapse of the Soviet Union still faces problems caused by the territorial policies of the Tsarist and Soviet empires. Therefore, it is extremely important to study the ethno-demographic landscape of any region and city of Azerbaijan in previous stages of history. This will help to determine the number of Azerbaijanis and other peoples who have historically lived in the region during different periods of history.

It is challenging to determine the number and composition of people who lived in Nakhchivan during the 19th and early 20th centuries due to the scarcity of written sources. However, analyzing the notes of travelers of that time and studying some archival documents can help us find answers to some of the research questions. In foreign historiography, several authors such as I. Chopin, G. Druville, K. Nikitin, N. Shavrov, and A. Altstadt have provided information on this topic [30; 13; 22; 29; 2]. I. Chopin, a civil consultant and ethnographer who led the work on the population census studied the issues that related to the annexation of Azerbaijani territories to the Russian Empire. In his essay, Chopin provides information about the geography and socio-economic situation of Azerbaijani territories. He also discusses the ethno-demographic processes that occurred before and after the occupation of Russia. The scholar explains the settlement of Armenians in former Iravan and Nakhchivan Khanates and reasons for the Armenian demographic growth from his points of view. Although flawed and biased, and written in accordance with the requirements of the imperial policy of tsarism it is important to consider the work as a source for studying the research question. Additionally, the State Historical Archive of the Azerbaijan Republic contains

various sources such as the "Statistical Description of the Nakhchivan Province", "Caucasian Calendar", "Acts of the Caucasian Archaeographic Commission", and various collections published in the Russian Empire, which provide valuable information about the object of research.

This topic is considered one of the most significant issues in Azerbaijani history and is the subject of national historiography. Prior to the 19th century, the "Overview Notebook of the Yerevan Province" that was interpreted and translated by academician Bunyadov and historian Mammadov contained some information about the ethnic makeup of the population and the demographic situation in the cities of Iravan and Nakhchivan. During the late 16th and early 17th centuries, as well as in the 1720s and 1730s, Nakhchivan was one of the administrative-territorial units of the Ravan (Iravan) province of Chukhursad, along with other Azerbaijani lands, under the rule of the Ottoman Empire. These pre-Afshar materials are important for studying the origins of the ethno-democratic landscape that existed in the 19th century.

In national historiography, many issues related to this topic were studied by S. Budagova, H. Verdieva, T. Mustafazadeh, N. Guliyev, Z. Shahverdiev, I. Musaev [3; 12; 19; 18; 9; 8].

The article will attempt to explore the impact of political and demographic changes on the ethnic situation of the region that occurred after the mass Armenian migrations to the region. The comparative analysis was used for this study.

Analysis of the ethno-democratic landscape of Nakhchivan before the Turkmenchay Treaty

Information dating back to the end of the 16th century suggests that some of the Muslim population living in Iravan and Nakhchivan were either taken as prisoners or resettled by the Ottomans to their provinces. The authors of "Nusratnama" and "Zafarnama" mention the resettlement of Ali Bey, who lived in the Abaran region with over 3,000 people, to the province of Erzurum in the 1670s. He was appointed as Beylarbey of the Tükrman sanjak. The same sources indicate that Ottoman troops from Kars captured around 20,000 people from Sharur county in 1579 [7, p.327]. In 1578, Sultan Murad III issued a decree that protected tax-paying Armenians and Kurds (this decree did not apply to Qizilbash Kurds) from persecution. The Ottomans usually persecuted Shiite Muslims. Therefore, Armenians and Kurds were not among the imprisoned or resettled populations. That's why the accuracy of the "Notebooks" of 1728, which reported that 43,784 people (61.2%) were Muslim Turks and 27,799 people (38.8%) were Christians [6, p.14], should be approached with caution and a critical eye. The general ethnic composition of the Turkish-Muslim population of the Iravan province was also negatively affected by historical events of previous periods. In general, the Safavid-Ottoman wars had a serious impact on the ethnic composition of the population. The lack of accurate demographic information about the population during this period should be explained by the results of these wars.

"Notebooks of the Yerevan Province" contain facts about the demographic situation, topography, religious and social situation of the cities of the region. According to these data, at the end of the 16th century, 4,208 people lived in Nakhchivan, 2,000 in Iravan, and 1,357 people in Ordubad [6, p.15].

In his essay Sayahat-name the 17th century famous Turkish traveler Evliya Chelebi mentioned that in the city of Nakhchivan there are 10,000 large houses, 70 Friday mosques, 40 neighborhood mosques, 20 guest houses, 7 baths and more than 100 shops. Chalabi's information mentions only worships and mosques that belonged to Muslims. Chalabi didn't mention Christian monuments and churches which means the absence or a very small number of Christian elements in Nakhchivan during the specified period [27, p.114-115]. During the 1720s and 1730s, the city of Iravan, which was part of the Nakhchivan sanjak, saw an increase in its population. At that time, the city was home to 3,369 people. However, despite the population growth, the city's share of the overall population of the province decreased to 4.7% [6, p.15]. This can be reasonably associated with the Ottoman-Safavid wars, the occupation of the city by Ottoman troops in 1723.

According to archival documents and the account of the traveler Druvil [13, p. 18; 1, f. 24, op. 1, d. 353, l 6], who visited Nakhchivan in 1813, there was significant destruction in the city just before it was annexed to the Russian Empire under the Treaty of Gulistan. At that time, the population of Nakhchivan was recorded to be 4,360 people [18, p. 100].

Contemporaries have reported that before the Treaty of Turkmenchay, Armenians lived only in 62 out of 1111 settlements in the Iravan province. Similarly, only 12 out of 231 villages registered in the Nakhchivan and Ordubad regions were inhabited by Armenians. According to I. Chopin, 752 villages were inhabited in the "Armenian province," out of which 359 were completely destroyed and some were even forgotten [30, p.509-510, p.599-634]. The source compiled by Vasily Grigoriev in 1833 provides information about only 434 Armenian families living in Nakhchivan before the Treaty of Turkmenchay [26, p.31].

According to demographic data before the signing of the Turkmenchay Treaty, 8,567 families (about 40,248 people) lived in Nakhchivan, and 31,201 families (about 164,450 people) lived in Iravan, Nakhchivan regions and Ordubad district [30, p.638-642]. The author mentions that representatives of the Armenian people were present in 62 villages, which indicates that they made up approximately 5% of the population in those settlements. It is important to note that the author does not state that these villages were entirely Armenian, but rather that there were Armenians among the population. Therefore, it can be assumed that the statistics provided by Vasily Grigoriev, which reflect a total of 434 Armenian families in the Nakhchivan region, are logical and accurate.

Ethnodemographic indicators of Nakhchivan after the signing of the Turkmenchay Treaty

Nakhchivan was one of the Azerbaijani khanates that was annexed by Tsarist Russia in 1828 under the Treaty of Turkmenchay with the Gajar state. The same year, it was included in the so-called "Armenian region" [11, p.487], along with the Yerevan Province, on the initiative of the commander of the Russian troops in the Caucasus, I. Paskevich, by decree of Emperor Nicholas I on March 21. In 1840, Nakhchivan was included in the Iravan district, and in 1849 in the Iravan province. At that time, the Nakhchivan region consisted of five provinces - Alinjachay, Nakhchivan, Mavazikhatun, Khok and Darelayaz, and the Ordubad region - from the Ordubad, Aylis, Dastiya, Bilyav and Chenab provinces [30, p.599-634]. On February 29, 1828, at the direction of the Tsarist General I.F. Paskevich, a "Special Committee" was created under the "Iravan Provisional Administration" and its Nakhchivan branch, consisting of one staff officer, two senior officers and two Christians [25, p.86].

Article 15 of the Turkmenchay Treaty created favorable conditions for the free movement of Armenians through the Araz to the "Russian provinces" (newly annexed territories of Azerbaijan). The Ghajar state also promised not to interfere with those wishing to move and set a five-year period for the free movement, delivery and sale of movable property without imposing any duties or taxes on it. Armenians played a special role in the resettlement policy of Tsarist Russia. To begin with, Armenians, being Eastern Christians, were more adaptable to the living conditions in the eastern countries that were occupied by Russia than other communities. Additionally, they lived in Muslim states and territories, under the governance of rulers of a different religion and language. Moreover, Armenians were more fluent in Eastern languages, knew Muslim traditions, and their ways of life better. This made it easier for them to acclimatize to the changing political, religious, and legal conditions imposed by foreign rulers [12, p.36].

After the South Caucasus was occupied, the "Armenian region" was established in the Iravan and Nakhchivan khanates. This administrative unity served as a military and political outpost for the empire. As a result, the "Armenian province" was immediately included in the cameral list by order of I. Paskevich, following a royal decree. This task was assigned to I. Chopin, a civil consultant and ethnographer.

As per the directives of Ivan Paskevich, the commander-in-chief of Russian troops in the Caucasus, settlers were instructed not to be relocated to state lands. Instead, most of them were resettled on private lands belonging to Azerbaijanis. This resulted in the displacement of semi-nomadic Azerbaijanis who were staying in summer pastures. These Azerbaijanis were unable to return to their homes. Griboyedov, who confirmed this fact, noted that Armenians began to settle more on the lands of Muslim landowners after the Turkmenchay Treaty. The oppression faced by Muslims led to their discontent [14, p.15.]. The discontent between the local population and the resettled Armenians was felt more in Nakhchivan. Therefore, at the suggestion of Alexander Griboedov, 500 Armenian families who settled in

Muslim lands of the Nakhchivan region were resettled to Darelayaz [11, p.647-648]. Despite the measures taken, in 1828-1829 the number of Azerbaijani families living in Nakhchivan decreased to 2,770 (or 60%) as a result of the departure of a large number of Azerbaijanis, who made up more than 90% (about 1,400 families) of the population [26, p.30]. Another reason for the decline in the Turkic-Muslim population in Nakhchivan, as in other cities and villages of Azerbaijan, was the wars that brought great destruction at the end of the 18th and first decades of the 19th century.

Speaking about the need for Russian colonization of the Caucasus and "strengthening the Russian people" in this region, scholar N. Shavrov writes: "After the end of the Russian-Iranian war (1826-1828), during 1828-1830, we resettled 40,000 Armenians from Persia and 84,000 Armenians from Turkiye and placed them in Elizavetpol, Yerevan and Tiflis districts, where Armenians made up a small part of the population. "An allocation of 200 thousand dessiatines of government land was made for the Armenians. Over 2 million rubles were spent on purchasing land from Muslims for their settlement. These Armenians settled in the mountainous part of the Elizavetpol province and along the banks of the Geycha River. It should be noted that while the official number of Armenians resettled here was 124,000 people, many more were resettled unofficially. In total, it is estimated that over 200,000 Armenians were resettled in this region." [29, p.64].

In the two years after the signing of the Turkmenchay Treaty - in 1828-1829 - 6,976 Armenian families or 35,560 people were resettled to the lands of Northern Azerbaijan, of which 2,557 families were resettled in the Nakhchivan province (416 families in cities, 1,869 families in villages). The number of Armenian families settled in Ordubad was 266. After these relocations, the number of Armenian families in Nakhchivan increased to 2991, the vast majority of which were resettled from Salmas, Khoy, Urmia and other villages and cities of Southern Azerbaijan [26, p.31, 125-127]. According to another source, in the 1830s, 1,884 Azerbaijani and 1,606 resettled Armenian families lived in 59 villages of the Nakhchivan region. Of the 1,330 families living in the city of Nakhchivan, 905 were Azerbaijani and 425 were resettled Armenian families [23, p.332].

Armenians settled not only in villages with fertile lands of the South Caucasus, but also in cities. As a result, the two main cities of Nakhchivan region - Nakhchivan and Ordubad - underwent serious ethno-demographic changes. According to sources, in the first years of occupation, 1,330 families or 5,470 people lived in the city of Nakhchivan, and 803 families or 3,444 people lived in the city of Ordubad. So, in total, there were 2133 families, or 8914 families in two cities [30, p. 635-636].

Sources confirm that at the time of signing the Turkmenchay Treaty there were 873 houses and 1,330 families in Nakhchivan. According to these documents, the Armenians resettled in the city after the Russian invasion made up 1/5 of the population. Out of 5,470 residents of the city, 1,110 people were Armenians [1, f. 24, op. 1, d. 353, l. 8-9]. Chopin, who wrote that on the

eve of the Russian invasion there were about 200 villages on the territory of Nakhchivan, clarifies that after the invasion, in 1829, there were 7,974 Armenians (4,192 men and 3,782 women) and 8,553 Tatars (herein after Azerbaijanis) in the region, of which 4,538 were men and 4,015 women. The author writes that 3,550 Armenians (1,818 men and 1,732 women) and 3,985 Azerbaijanis (2,064 men and 1,921 women) lived in the Ordubad region; 3,508 Armenians (1,833 men and 1,675 women) and 4,405 Azerbaijanis (2,619 men and 1,786 women) lived in the Daralayaz region [30, p.556-564, 599-630, 638-642]. According to I. Chopin, in 1832 the population of Nakhchivan was 5,470 people, of which 3,641 were Azerbaijanis and 1,448 were Armenians. 338 Armenians were local, and 1,110 were resettled from Iran after the Treaty of Turkmenchay. There were 3,262 Azerbaijanis and 182 Armenians living in the city of Ordubad, that is, a total of 3,444 people [30, p. 479-482].

In 1850, 4,410 people were registered in Nakhchivan, 3,973 people in Ordubad (total 8,383 people). According to the results of a desk survey conducted in 1873, 6,877 people lived in Nakhchivan, and 3,489 people lived in Ordubad. That is a total of 10,366 people lived in the Nakhchivan region. As for the ethnic composition of the city's population, the number of Armenians living in Nakhchivan was 2,167 people (1,191 men and 976 women), and the number of Azerbaijanis was 4,694 people (2,523 men and 2,171 women). 360 Armenians (212 men and 148 women) and 3,131 Azerbaijanis (1,853 men, 1,278 women) lived in Ordubad [15, p.248].

Throughout the 19th century, Armenians continued to migrate to the South Caucasus region. This trend persisted following the Russian-Turkish wars of 1853-1856 and 1877-1878, during which a significant number of Armenians from Eastern Anatolia were resettled in the Iravan province. According to data for 1873, the number of Armenians in Nakhchivan district was 17,468 people (9,465 men and 8,003 women), in Ordubad district - 7,864 people (4,453 men and 3,411 women), in Darelayaz district - 11,473 people (6,099 men and 5,374 women). The Turkic-Muslim population was 20,836 (12,209 men and 8,627 women), 9,593 (5,717 men and 3,876 women) and 18,040 (9,846 men and 8,194 women) respectively. Additionally, 244 Russians (Molokans) of both sexes are registered in the region [15, p. 209-276].

According to the 1886 census, there were 6,939 people in Nakhchivan and 4,199 in Ordubad (11,138 people in total). According to the 1897 census, 8,790 people were registered in the city of Nakhchivan, and 4,611 in Ordubad - a total of 13,401 people [24, p.2.].

Based on data from 1896, it was found that Nakhchivan had five mosques, three Armenian Apostolic churches, and one Eastern Orthodox Church. This information allows us to draw conclusions about the ethnic and demographic makeup of the city's population [21]. The Muslim-Turkic population was the most dominant in the region. Historical records suggest that there were 70 Congregational mosques and 40 other mosques in Nakhchivan during the mid-17th century.

In addition, there were also the mosques of Sultan Murad and Hazrat Pasha [6, p. 19, 20; 27. p. 12]. However, by the end of the 19th century, the number of religious houses in the region had decreased significantly. Chardin, who visited Nakhchivan in the 18th century, confirms that the city was gradually rebuilt after 80% of it was destroyed. The city originally had 40,000 houses. Chardin attributes the destruction to the order of Shah Abbas Safavid, who achieved his military goals. As a result of this policy, the population was displaced from the region and defense structures were destroyed [28, p. 63].

According to the 1897 all-Russian census, the population of Nakhchivan district was 100,771. 63.66 Azerbaijanis and 34.41 Armenians resided in the area. Data showed 67.36 Azerbaijanis and 27.08 Armenians registered in Sharur-Daralayaz. Researcher Z. Shahverdiyev has pointed out that the combined data for the Sharur-Daralayaz region makes it difficult to draw accurate conclusions. He notes that ignoring the population of Sadarak has led to a reduction in the estimated population of the Nakhchivan region. Therefore, the researcher assumes that around 150,000 people lived in the region by the end of the 19th century [9. p.70.].

Ethnodemographic situation in Nakhchivan at the beginning of the 20th century

Italian traveler Luigi Villari, who visited Nakhchivan at the beginning of the 20th century, noted that the Azerbaijanis in Nakhchivan were richer than the Armenians, and most of the land belonged to them. Armenians worked as workers on their estates [10, p. 267].

At the beginning of the 20th century, the ethnodemographic map of Nakhchivan, along with Iravan, Zangezur and Karabakh, was seriously damaged as a result of ethnic conflicts and massacres provoked by Russian Tsarism. Historian E. Jafarli notes that the number of Azerbaijanis in Nakhchivan in 1907, compared to 1897, decreased to 31,279 people (34.6%), and as a result of the massacre of 1905-1907, the reduction was almost 2 times [4, p.181].

According to the "Caucasian calendar" there were 9,000 inhabitants in the city in 1915. Over 2,000 of them were Muslims, over 2,000 were Armenians and about 200 were Russians [17]. In 1917, about 240 rural-type settlements were registered in the region [1, f.379, op.3, d. 5901, l.6]. Considering that on the eve of the Turkmenchay Treaty there were 200 villages in Nakhchivan, we can say that the number of villages increased.

In 1916, 81,708 (59%) Azerbaijanis and 54,209 (40%) Armenians lived in the Nakhchivan district. In Sharur-Daralayaz district, these figures were 60,183 (66.7%) and 29,165 (32.3%), respectively. In 1917, in Nakhchivan district, 83,276 people (59.4%) were Azerbaijanis, and 50,193 people (39.6%) were Armenians. In Sharur-Daralayaz district 82,607 people (68%) were Azerbaijanis, 31,999 people (31%) were Armenians. In the Zangazur region, 123,085 (55%) Azerbaijanis and 99,257 (44.3%) Armenians were registered [8, p. 48-49]. The author mentioned certain figures for the year 1917 without specifying the exact months. However, it can be assumed that the population of the Nakhchivan

region increased towards the end of that year. According to the documents from the State Historical Archive of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the population of the Nakhchivan district was 122,208, Sharur had 40,000 residents, and the city of Nakhchivan had 8,934 inhabitants, making a total of 171,142 people living in the Nakhchivan district altogether, just before the October Revolution [1, f.379, op.3, d 5901, l.6]. According to the "Caucasian calendar" 8934 people lived in Nakhchivan, 5717 people lived in Ordubad, and in total there were 14651 urban population in Nakhchivan in 1917 [20, p.217-219].

When discussing the ethnic and demographic changes that occurred in the 19th and early 20th centuries, it's important to note that not only Armenians but also Russians, specifically exiled sectarians from the internal provinces of the Russian Empire, settled in Azerbaijan. These migrations continued throughout the 19th century, and by 1916, the number of Russians who had never previously resided in Azerbaijan had reached around 250,000. New settlements were established, and the best plots of land were allocated in several regions of Azerbaijan, including the village of Bichenak (Karmalinovka) in Nakhchivan district for Russian settlers. According to D. Ismailzade, the village had a population of 164 people of both sexes in the 1930s-1980s. The population grew to 280 between mid-1980s and 1904, and then reached 310 people from 1905 to 1917 [16, p.294].

In 1918, because of attacks by Dashnak detachments on Nakhchivan, part of the local Azerbaijani population was killed, and some left their places of residence. On January 4, 1919, the population of Nakhchivan appealed to the Chairman of the Council of Ministers of the Azerbaijan Republic, Fatali Khan Khoyski. The report said that from December 1917 to June 1918, more than 200 Muslim villages were burned, and their inhabitants were killed by Armenian military units, in the Surmaly, Echmiadzin and Sharur districts of the Iravan governorate. The population abandoned their homes and fled to the mountains and the Iranian border [1, f. 894, op. 10, d 37, l.9]. In December 1919, Armenian troops moved from Yerevan and laid siege to eight Muslim villages around Sadarak, according to press reports [5, p. 40].

The Azerbaijani Embassy in Tehran also reported regular attacks by Armenian militants in Nakhchivan and Ordubad. Adil Khan Ziyadkhanov, in his report to the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Azerbaijan dated April 10, 1919, mentioned the active participation of Iranian Armenians in these attacks [1, f. 970, op. 1, d. 127, l. 2]. These events had a serious impact on the decline of the Azerbaijani population in Nakhchivan.

Conclusion

Nakhchivan, an ancient settlement of the Turkic tribes, experienced significant changes in its population composition due to various political events during the 19th and early 20th centuries. The Russian-Iranian wars turned Nakhchivan into a battlefield, resulting in a negative impact on the city's appearance and its demographic data.

After the signing of the Turkmenchay Treaty, Nakhchivan became one of the historical territories of

Azerbaijan that underwent the policy of "Armenization", "Christianization" and turned into a center of genocide of the population. According to sources, it can be noted that the resettlement policy seriously affected the situation of the local Muslim population, and many families left their places of residence because of discontent. Because of the 15th article of the Turkmenchay Treaty, which was highly advantageous for Armenians, the number of Armenians resettled from Iran to Nakhchivan was artificially increased. As a result, by the beginning of the 20th century, their population in this area had reached 14-16%.

Based on the research's sources, we have concluded that the city in question never belonged to the Armenian people, despite claims made by Armenian researchers. The Azerbaijani Turks were one of the most ancient and indigenous peoples of the region, including the territory of modern Armenia. Toponymic information is particularly important in determining the composition of a population and proving a specific area belongs to a certain people. Therefore, toponymic names and names of settlements are also served as a source to determine the ethnic composition of the population of Nakhchivan.

Between 1918 and 1920, one of the main goals of the Armenians was to capture Nakhchivan. In November 1919, Armenian nationalists launched an armed attack on Nakhchivan, captured part of Zangazur, and cut off Nakhchivan from Azerbaijan. However, this was not enough for them as they continued to pursue their goal of claiming Nakhchivan and demanded the repeal of international agreements between Moscow and Kars that prevented this.

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